

Synthesis of 2,5 Disubstituted Oxazoles

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2,5-Disubstituted oxazoles are commonly used in scintillation spectrometry. The present study deals in the synthesis of commonly used scintillator solutes viz., 2-phenyl-5-aryloxazoles, 2-(4-biphenyl)-5-aryloxazoles and 1,4-di-[2(5-aryloxazolyl)]-benzene. Acylation of aromatic hydrocarbons by hippuryl chloride(I), *p*-phenyl-hippuryl chloride (II) and terephthalyl diglycyl chloride (III) in the presence of aluminium chloride gives corresponding N-substituted and N-N'-substituted amides which on cyclodehydration yield respective oxazoles. NMR studies of some of the amides and oxazoles has been made and the data obtained is discussed.

The demand for scintillation chemicals is increasing with increasing use of radioactive isotopes. This necessitates the development of new methods to improve upon the available procedures for the synthesis of scintillation chemicals. Some oxazoles are well known for their usefulness in scintillation studies¹⁻⁷ and the present study was taken up to explore the possibility of extending the acylation of aromatic hydrocarbons with acid chlorides in the presence of aluminium chloride to get the corresponding amides. These amides on cyclodehydration gave the desired oxazoles.

II and III were prepared by the action of PCl_5 on the corresponding acids using acetyl chloride as solvent. They were isolated as anilides. The N-substituted and N,N'-substituted amides were prepared by slow addition of anhydrous aluminium chloride to a suspension of corresponding acid chloride and hydrocarbon in dry solvent. Either the hydrocarbon itself or carbon disulphide was used as solvent. Reaction conditions, yields and their characteristics are summarised in Table 1.

The structure of first three amides was studied with the help of Varian A-60A, NMR spectrometer. In all the cases the absorption by $-\text{CONH}-$ proton was overlapped by the aromatic multiplet centered around $\delta 7.5$. This was detected by the absorption at $\delta 5$ of methylene protons splitting into a doublet ($J = 4$ cps) due to the coupling with adjacent NH proton and by proton counting. This was confirmed further by labelling the NH proton with deuterium wherein the doublet of methylene protons collapsed into a sharp singlet. The downfield absorption of enolic proton was not observed indicating the absence of enolisation of these ketonic amides under the prevailing conditions. The NMR spectra of other amides in Table 1 could not be studied as they are insoluble in the common solvents used for analysis.

The amides on refluxing with POCl_3 are converted to oxazoles by cyclodehydration. Their yields and characteristics are summarised in Table 2.

TABLE 1

Sl.No.	Ar ₁	Ar ₂	Hydro-carbon (moles)	Acid (moles)	AlCl ₃ (moles)	Sol-vent* (ml.)	Temp. (°C)	R.S.**	M.P. (°C)	Lit. m.p. (°C)	Yield*** (%)
1.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	0.10	0.10	0.30	200	46	E	114-6	114 ⁴	48
2.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	0.10	0.10	0.30	300	46	E	178-80	185.6 ⁴	40
3.	C ₆ H ₅	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	0.10	0.10	0.30	450	0-10	E	146-7	148 ⁴	25
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	0.10	0.10	0.30	150 ^a	80	E	178-80	181 ⁵	42-43
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	0.10	0.10	0.30	150 ^b	30	E	187	186 ⁵	38
6.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	0.10	0.10	0.30	100	46	C-E	256-7	259 ⁵	88
7.	Ar ₃ =	C ₆ H ₅	0.20	0.10	0.60	500 ^a	20-30	D	274-7	262.8 ⁷	60
8.	Ar ₃ =	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	0.20	0.10	0.60	250	20-30	D	281-3	282 ⁵	38
9.	Ar ₃ =	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	0.20	0.10	0.60	250	20-30	D	298-302	250 ⁷	30

* For 'a' & 'b' benzene and toluene was used respectively. In all other cases CS₂ was used.

** R.S.—Recrystallising solvent, E—ethanol, C—chloroform, D—N, N-dimethylformamide.

*** Based on acid chlorides which was determined from their corresponding anilides.

TABLE 2

No.	Ar ₁	Ar ₂	R.S.*	M.P. (°C)	Lit.m.p. (°C)	Yield (%)
1.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	E	74	75 ⁴	75
2.	C ₆ H ₅	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	E	155	157 ⁴	75
3.	C ₆ H ₅	1-C ₁₀ H ₇	E	108-9	112 ⁴	70
4.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅	E	109	110 ⁵	51
5.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	E	154	153-4 ⁵	49-50
6.	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	C-E	230-1	232-3 ⁵	48
7.	Ar ₃ =	C ₆ H ₅	G	243-4	273-8 ⁷	76
8.	Ar ₃ =	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	G	250-2	254-5 ⁵	66-67
9.	Ar ₃ =	<i>p</i> -C ₆ H ₅ C ₆ H ₄	P	288-90	292-4 ⁷	65

*R.S.—recrystallising solvent, E—ethanol, C—chloroform, G—glacial acetic acid, P—pyridine.

The NMR analysis of first three oxazoles shows the complex multiplet of aromatic protons from 7.41 δ —8.41 δ . The absorption of the proton of the oxazole ring appears to be overlapped by this multiplet which can be inferred from the spectra of other 2,5-disubstituted oxazoles reported⁸ earlier. This has been further confirmed here by proton counting in case of 2-phenyl-5-*p*-tolylloxazole. Spectra of other oxazoles could not be taken due to their insolubility in common solvents for NMR analysis.

It can be seen that the acid chlorides I, II and III are effective acylating agents in the presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride. The present method gives better yields and involves less number of intermediates than the general method of preparation of 2,5-disubstituted oxazoles starting from acetophenone^{2,6,7}. It is also comparable with the methods^{4,5} where acid azalactones are used as acylating agents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Varian A-60A NMR spectrometer was used. Chemical shifts are recorded in parts per million (δ) relative to internal TMS standard. CDCl_3 was used as solvent.

Preparation of II : PCl_5 (25 gms., 0.12 moles) was added to a suspension of *p*-phenyl-hippuric acid⁵ (25.5 gms., 0.1 moles) in a freshly distilled acetyl chloride (500 ml), at room temperature. To initiate the reaction, the mixture was slightly warmed and it was kept for two hours with intermittent shaking. The insoluble solid was filtered, washed with acetylchloride and dry petroleum ether. M.P. of the product was 171°–4° with decomposition. Yield : 22 gms.

Anilide of II was prepared by refluxing the above product with aniline (0.25 moles) using dry benzene (200 ml) as solvent for two hours. M.P. 251°–2°. Yield 42% reconned on acid.

Analysis-Found : C 75.91, H 5.26, N 8.75; Cal. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C 76.66, H 5.45; N 8.48%.

Preparation of III : To a suspension of terephthalyl diglycine⁹ (28 gm., 0.1 mole) in acetyl chloride (500 ml) PCl_5 (45.7 gms., 0.22 mole) was added at room temperature. Reaction mixture was gently refluxed for 1½ hr. The insoluble solid was filtered, washed with acetyl chloride and dry petroleum ether. M.P. of the product was 245°–8° with decomposition. Yield : 28 gms.

Anilide of III was prepared by refluxing the above product with aniline (0.45 mole) in benzene (250 ml) for 2 hrs. M.P. 318°–21° with decomposition, Yield : 50% reconned on acid.

Analysis-Found : C 65.96; H 5.17; N 12.07 : Calc. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$: C 66.99; H 5.11; N 13.02%.

N-substituted and *N,N'*-substituted amides : These are prepared by slow addition of anhydrous aluminium chloride to a suspension of acid chloride and aromatic hydrocarbon in dry solvent at 0°–10°. It was then stirred for 5 hrs at the temperature indicated in Table 1 and kept overnight. The mixture was decomposed by slowly pouring it into cold

dilute HCl. The amide, thus obtained, was filtered, washed with water and then with sodium bicarbonate solution. Dried in air and recrystallised from the solvents as mentioned in Table 1.

2,5-Disubstituted oxazoles : Amide (1 gm.) was refluxed with POCl_3 (60 ml) for 12 hrs. The excess POCl_3 was distilled and the residue was poured into the ice water mixture. Thus precipitated oxazoles were filtered, dried in air and recrystallised from the solvents as mentioned in Table 2.

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REFERENCES

1. S. D. Paul, P. S. Juneja and D. L. Dhane, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 760.
2. F. N. Hayes, Report No. LA-1639 (Group H-4), Los Alamos Scientific Laboratory, University of California, October 1953.
3. R. C. Sangaster and J. W. Irvine, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **24**, 670.
4. P. T. Frangopal, A. T. Balaban, L. Birladeanu and E. Cioranescu, *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **16**, 59.
5. A. T. Balaban, Ionna Belly, P. T. Frangopal, Maria Bascesu, E. Cioranescu and L. Birladeanu, *Tetrahedron*, 1963, **19**, 169.
6. G. Vasvari, *Intern. J. appl. radiation isotopes*, 1965, **16**, 327.
7. F. N. Hayes, B. S. Rogers and D. G. Ott, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1850.
8. D. J. Brown and P. B. Ghosh, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 270.
9. C. S. Cleaver and B. C. Pratt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1544.